

Enhancement of Power System Performance under Wind Generator Penetration with considering Cost Saving

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Abstract – Power system stability affected by wind generators penetration increasing. Genetic Algorithm (GA) is used in this paper to allocate and select the suitable size of the TCSCs devices to reduce this effect of wind generators penetration. To examine the method two cases studied on IEEE 9 bus and IEEE 39 bus systems with wind generator absorb reactive power from the system. In all cases, the power system indices as minimum voltage and losses have not acceptable values. Results found that TCSCs devices can enhance the power system indices and make suitable cost saving through the management of line active and reactive flow.

Keywords: Wind power, Flexible AC transmission systems, power system analysis and cost saving

I. Introduction

Renewable energy as wind generators is one of the important sources of energy nowadays but it has an advantage and disadvantage listed in [1] should be considered when it is used. One of the most problems of wind energy, that the operator may disconnect the wind generator to keep the voltage at suitable level.

Loss reduction is one of the important issues associated with wind generation penetration. This reduction can be achieved through capacitor placement as in [2] but FACTS devices used in the presented article are more flexible than the capacitors.

References [3-5] considered TCSCs as a most technological type of FACTS which can enhance power system performance under wind generator high penetration.

A lot of TCSCs models explained in [5-7], Model in Figure 1 is considered in this article which explained in details in reference [5]. The model is a combination of variable reactance and capacitor. The compensation level is the resultant of the reactance and capacitor. The range of TCSCs is considered -30% to -70% and -80% to 20% of line reactance (X_{line}) to avoid resonance.

Fig. 1 Model of TCSCs [5]

Several research articles considered the FACTS devices as a solution for voltage stability, reactive power compensation problems, frequency deviation problems, oscillation of power and transient problems associated with wind penetration increasing as explained in details in [8-18]

This article tries to enhance power system indices which are suffered from wind generator high penetration, through the optimal location of TCSCs. Reduction of losses is considered as the objective function without any power system indices violated. The wind generator is studied as a steady state generator absorbs reactive power from the network which can be considered as fixed type wind generator. This case is more difficult than the variable type of wind generators, where the variable type of wind generator can produce its own reactive power. This work studied several levels of reactive power absorbed by the wind generator from the network also studied the cost saving which TCSCs can achieve.

II. Proposed Optimization Technique

This article considered GA method to optimal location and sizing of TCSCs. The GA aspects are considered as the default of Matlab R2007a. GA will first try to found the location of TCSCs which will be binary population then the results go to another GA to found the optimal sizing of TCSCs as program given in [19] with objective try to reduce total active loss without any power system indices violated. MATPOWER is used to calculate total active loss from running system power flow [20]. The reactance of each line is updated with the value of TCSCs reactance as shown in (1)

$$\text{Updated reactance} = \text{reactance of line} + \text{TCSCs reactance} \quad (1)$$

III. Contribution of Paper

- Tool to optimize the location and sizing of TCSCs.
- Use the TCSCs to obtain cost saving through reduction of total active losses which not considered in several research papers.
- Proving that series FACTS effectiveness in solving problems associated with wind generators penetration.

IV. Case Study 1

The system under study is considered as IEEE 9 bus systems as shown in Figure 2. An author of [20] gives the data of the system in details. Reactive power absorbed by wind generator at bus 2 is considered 20 % and 40% of its rated. In "20%" studying two ranges of TCSCs are considered (capacitive and capacitive-inductive). But in "40%" the best range of the two ranges only considered in the study.

Fig. 2 IEEE 9-bus systems

V. Simulation Results

Simulation results show power flow in all lines is within the limits shown in [20]. Table 1 shows the system parameters profile with reactive power absorbed by wind generator is considered 20 % of its rated.

TABLE 1
SYSTEM PARAMETERS PROFILE WITH REACTIVE POWER ABSORBED BY WIND GENERATOR IS CONSIDERED 20 % OF ITS RATED.

	Without FACTS	With TCSC capacitive range (-0.7 to -0.3 Xline)	With TCSC inductive - capacitive range (-0.8 to 0.2 Xline)
Total loss % of load	2.016	1.67	1.71
Vmax (pu)	1	1	1
Vmin (pu)	0.875	0.974	0.961
Power angle max (degree)	12.65	7.37	11.2
Power angle min (degree)	-4.53	-2.01	-2.7
Q at wind bus (MVar)		-32.6	

As shown in Table 1, with reactive power absorbed by wind generator is 32.6 MVar (20% of wind generator rating) it can be found that TCSCs insertion can improve

minimum voltage to over than 0.9 pu also can make a suitable reduction in power loss.

TABLE 2
COST SAVING IN %20 REACTIVE POWER ABSORBED BY WIND GENERATOR - CAPACITIVE RANGE

Capacitive range				
TCSCs rating (MVar)	TCSCs price million \$	Reduction in Power loss (MW)	Reduction *in Power loss million \$	Net difference between reduction in loss & TCSCs prices million \$ In one year
0.42	0.065	1.09	0.764	0.699

TABLE 3
COST SAVING IN %20 REACTIVE POWER ABSORBED BY WIND GENERATOR - CAPACITIVE-INDUCTIVE RANGE

Capacitive-inductive range				
TCSCs rating MVar	TCSCs price million \$	Reduction in Power loss (MW)	Reduction *in Power loss million \$	Net Difference between reduction in loss & TCSCs prices million \$ In one year
0.292	0.045	0.96	0.673	0.63

*Price of energy loss is considered 10 cents / KWH, load factor=0.8

According to [21] cost of TCSCs can be as in (2)

$$C_{TCSC} = 0.0015 S^2 - 0.713 S + 153.75 (\$/kVAr) \quad (2)$$

From case 1 the capacitive range (c range) is the best range. Another study is carried out but with reactive power absorbed by wind generator is considered 40 % of its rated on only the more effective range (the capacitive range):

Table 4 shows the system parameters profile with reactive power absorbed by wind generator is considered 40 % of its rated on the capacitive range.

TABLE 4
SYSTEM PARAMETERS PROFILE WITH REACTIVE POWER ABSORBED BY WIND GENERATOR IS CONSIDERED 40 % OF ITS RATED

	Without FACTS	With TCSC capacitive range
Total loss % of load	3.073	1.86
Vmax (pu)	1	1
Vmin (pu)	0.733	0.949
Power angle max (degree)	17.18	2.96
Power angle min (degree)	-4.91	-2.43
Q at wind bus (MVar)		-65.2

As shown in table 4, with reactive power absorbed by wind generator bus is 65.2 MVar (40 % of wind generator rating) , it can be found that TCSCs insertion can improve minimum voltage to over than 0.9 pu also

can make suitable reduction in power loss. Table 5 shows the cost saving in this case.

TABLE 5
COST SAVING IN %40 REACTIVE POWER INJECTED

Capacitive range				
TCSCs rating MVar	TCSCs price million \$	Reduction in Power loss MW	Reduction *in Power loss million \$	Net difference between reduction in loss & TCSCs prices million \$ In one year
1.044	0.1613	3.821	2.678	2.517

It is cleared that TCSC with capacitive range can solve the problem associated with wind penetration and make acceptable cost saving. Table 6 shows the FACTS values and location in the cases studied.

TABLE 6
FACTS VALUES AND LOCATIONS

Line connected buses	X_{line} (p.u.)	TCSC as a percentage of line reactance “%” reactive power injected to wind bus is 20% of wind generation Capacitive range	TCSC as a percentage of line reactance “%” reactive power injected to wind bus is 20% of wind generation Capacitive-inductive range	TCSC as a percentage of line reactance “%” reactive power injected to wind bus is 40% of wind generation Capacitive range
1-4	0.0576	-70	0	-70
4-5	0.092	0	-80	-30
5-6	0.17	0	0	-70
3-6	0.0586	0	-80	-70
6-7	0.1008	0	-80	-70
7-8	0.072	-70	-80	-70
8-2	0.0625	-70	0	-70
8-9	0.161	-30	0	-63.19
9-4	0.085	-70	-80	0

VI. Case Study 2

The modified IEEE-39 bus system is taken as the system under study. The single-line diagram of the system is shown in Fig. 3. The data of the system is taken from [20]. The cases under study are an outage of the largest generator with reactive power absorbed by the wind generator at bus 37 is 25% and 30 % of its power rating with load at bus 39 decreases from 1104 MW to 900 MW. These studies are carried out for a range of TCSC from -30% to -70% of the line reactance.

Fig. 3 Single-line diagram of modified IEEE-39 bus system [22]

VII. Simulation Results

Simulation results show power flow in all lines is within the limits shown in [23]. Table 7 shows the system parameters profile with reactive power absorbed by wind generator bus is 25% of wind generator rating.

TABLE 7
SYSTEM PARAMETERS PROFILE WITH REACTIVE POWER ABSORBED BY WIND GENERATOR BUS IS 25% OF WIND GENERATOR RATING

	Without FACTS	With FACTS
Total loss % of load	1.535	1.252
V_{max} (p.u.)	1.064	1.063
V_{min} (p.u.)	0.748	0.939
Power angle max (°)	0	0
Power angle min (°)	-55.88	-33.2
Q at wind bus (MVAR)	- 135	

As shown in Table 7, with 135 MVar (25% of wind generator rating) reactive powers absorbed by the wind generator bus, the following observations may be made:

- Without FACTS, the system suffers from the low minimum voltage (0.748 p.u.), high total losses and high power angle value (-55.88°).
- With series FACTS in range (-0.7 to -0.3 X_{line}) “c range” with adding only 8 devices as shown in Figure 4, the TCSCs insertion improves the voltage profile of the system to more than 0.9 pu and make a suitable reduction in power losses.

Fig. 4 Single-line diagram of modified IEEE-39 bus system with TCSC, 25 % reactive power injected

Figures from Fig. 5 to Fig. 7 show the summary of 25% reactive power absorbed by the wind generator bus

Fig. 5 Total loss with and without FACTS insertion, 25 % reactive power absorbed

Fig. 6 Minimum voltage with and without FACTS insertion, 25 % reactive power absorbed

Fig. 7 Power angle with and without FACTS insertion, 25 % reactive power absorbed

Table 8 shows the system parameters profile with reactive power absorbed by the wind generator bus is 35% of wind generator rating.

TABLE 8
SYSTEM PARAMETERS PROFILE WITH REACTIVE POWER ABSORBED BY THE WIND GENERATOR BUS IS 35% OF WIND GENERATOR RATING

	Without FACTS	With FACTS
Total loss % of load	1.613	1.351
V_{max} (p.u.)	1.063	1.064
V_{min} (p.u.)	0.727	0.905
Power angle max (°)	0	0
Power angle min (°)	-57.35	-40.11
Q at wind bus (MVAR)		-189

As shown in Table 8, with reactive power absorbed by wind generator is 189 MVAR (35% of wind generator rating), it can be found that:

- Without FACTS, the system suffers from the low minimum voltage (0.727 p.u.), high total losses and high power angle value (-57.35°).
- With series FACTS in range (-0.7 to -0.3 X_{line}) “c range” with adding only 7 devices as shown in Fig. 8, the minimum voltage increases to more than 0.9 pu and losses are minimized with acceptable value. It can be found that power angle is also reduced to -40.11°.

Fig. 8 Single-line diagram of modified IEEE-39 bus system with TCSC, 35 % reactive power absorbed

Figures from Fig. 9 to Fig. 11 show the summary of 35% reactive power absorbed by the wind generator bus.

Fig. 9 Total loss with and without FACTS insertion, 35 % reactive power absorbed

Fig. 10 Minimum voltage with and without FACTS insertion, 35 % reactive power absorbed

Fig. 11 Power angle with and without FACTS insertion, 35 % reactive power absorbed

Table 9 shows the FACTS values and location in the cases studied.

TABLE 9
FACTS VALUES AND LOCATIONS

From bus	To bus	Line reactance (p.u.)	A*	B*
1	2	0.0411	-66.08	-38.81
1	39	0.025	-70	-70
2	3	0.0151	-30	-70
2	25	0.0086	0	0
4	5	0.0128	-48.31	-30
5	6	0.0026	0	-70
5	8	0.0112	-36.26	0
7	8	0.0046	-70	-70
8	9	0.0363	-70	0
9	39	0.025	-70	-70

A* means TCSCs as a percentage of line reactance “%” in case of reactive power absorbed by the wind generator bus is 25% of wind generator rating and B* means TCSCs as a percentage of line reactance “%” in case of reactive power absorbed by the wind generator bus is 35% of wind generator rating

VIII. Cost Saving

Table 10 shows the cost saving with reactive power absorbed by the wind generator bus is 35% of wind generator rating.

TABLE 10
COST SAVING WITH REACTIVE POWER 35 % OF WIND GENERATOR RATING

TCSCs rating MVar	TCSCs price million \$	Reduction in Power loss (MW)	Reduction *in Power loss million \$	Net difference between reduction in power loss & TCSCs prices million \$ In one year
5.041	0.7572	15.59	10.92547	10.168

From Table 10, it is clear that TCSCs insertion can recover its cost beside operation enhancement.

IX. Conclusion

In this paper, optimal location of TCSCs devices are considered by using genetic algorithm optimization to reduce the problem associated with wind penetration in power systems. Cases studied are examined on modified IEEE 9 bus system and IEEE 39 bus system with change in reactive power absorbed by the wind generator from the network. Results show that series TCSCs with capacitive range is the best solution for this problem by controlling the reactive power flow in the system. Furthermore, it can be found that TCSCs insertion made an acceptable cost saving besides improving the power system indices.

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